

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE PRESENT IRANIANS

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Abstract : This in the article iranian of nations come output Iranian nations development and to small sub- families division ancient Bactria (now Afghanistan Tajikistan and Uzbekistan regions) in the area done increased Current at the time Iranian nations basically Iran , Afghanistan and Tajikistan , partially Uzbekistan , Pakistan , Turkey , Azerbaijan , Iraq , Syria , South Russia , Georgia and China in the regions wide prevalence about data statement done

Key words : Persian , Tajik , Pashtun , Pashai , sometimes Lagmani , Kurd , Mozandaran and Gilak , Choraymok , Hazaras .

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ИРАНЦЫ

Аннотация: В статье «Иранские нации» приведены результаты развития иранских наций и разделения на небольшие подсемейства древней Бактрии (ныне регионы Афганистана, Таджикистана и Узбекистана) в области, сделанной увеличенной. Текущие в то время иранские нации в основном Иран, Афганистан и Таджикистан, частично Узбекистан, Пакистан, Турция, Азербайджан, Ирак, Сирия, юг России, Грузия и Китай в регионах широкого распространения данных заявление сделано

Ключевые слова: персы, таджики, пуштуны, пашаи, иногда лагмани, курды, мозандаранцы и гилаки, хораймок, хазарейцы.

HOZIRGI ERONLAR

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada eron xalqlarining chiqishi Eron xalqlari taraqqiyoti va kichik bo'linmalarga qadimgi Baqtriya (hozirgi Afg'oniston Tojikiston va O'zbekiston viloyatlari) hududi bo'yicha ko'paydi Hozirgi vaqtda Eron xalqlari asosan Eron, Afg'oniston va Tojikiston qisman. O'zbekiston, Pokiston, Turkiya, Ozarbayjon, Iroq, Suriya, Janubiy Rossiya, Gruziya va Xitoy hududlarida keng tarqalgan ma'lumotlar bayonoti amalga oshirildi

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Kalit so'zlar: fors, tojik, pushtun, poshoy, ba'zan lag'mon, kurd, mozandaron va gilak, choraymoq, hazoralar.

Persians (pers ., river اى ران ى خا , crown fãrsãn , pãrsãn , irãnihã) — eng main and big iranian people Persians common the number each different to calculations from 40 million to 90 million person organize is enough and basically Iran , partially Afghanistan , Turkey and another in the states wide spread out . Basically islam of religion Shiite sect belief they do

Tajiks (Dari اى ران ى خا , crown fãrsãn , tãjikhã , Tajik . Farson , Tajikho) — to the Persians very near relative was and of them language , structure and culture according to very less distinguishable iranian people Tajiks common the number about 20-25 million people organize is enough and basically Tajikistan , Afghanistan , partially Uzbekistan , Iran and in Russia wide spread Basically islam of religion Sunni sect belief they do

Pashtuns , sometimes Afghans (Pusht . p s , twñ , in the west pařtún , in the east pařtún) is Eastern-Iranian people Many of them semi-nomadic . Iranian Pashto in the language they talk . Basically Afghanistan southern and eastern part , as well northern and western in Pakistan wide spread of Pashtuns common the number about 42-45 million people organize is enough Pashtuns basically islam of religion Sunni sect belief they do

Pashais , sometimes Laghmonites (Persian : پشها ى) - south-eastern iranian people Basically Afghanistan Acceptable and Kunar rivers and in the mountains of Pakistan Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in the region wide spread The Pashais the number about 100,000 people organize is enough Basically pashai in the language as well river and Pashtun in their languages they talk . Religion and belief according to the Pashaites basically islam of religion Sunni sect belongs to some while shia sect Ismaili to the flow belongs to

Kurds (Kurd . Kurd / kwrđ , Kurmancî / kwrmanj y) — West-Iranian people Basically present Turkey southeast , east and northern Iraq , west and north-west Iran , northern and eastern in Syria wide spread Tribal to divisions have is a Kurd of the language different in their dialects they talk . This idioms two big to the group : kurmanji (north Kurd language) and sorani (south Kurd language) to dialects is divided . Kurds to the ethnos also zazas and Goranis will also join . Kurds the number about 35-40 million people organize is enough Religion and belief according to

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basically islam of religion Sunni sect , as well shia and Alawite sect , Yezidism and Christian to religion is divided .

Baluchs (Baluch . بلوچ balōč) - semi-nomadic East-Iranian people Basically to the tribes is divided and of the Baloch the number about 10 million people organize is enough Basically of Pakistan Balochistan province of Afghanistan southeast part and of Iran Siston and Balochistan at the bottom wide spread Baloch basically islam of religion Sunni sect belongs to are considered

Mazandarans and Gilak (mozand . mżrwn y , مزرونی mazruni , topuri , gilak . گیلک gilāk) — to the Persians near relative considered iranian nations . of Iran northern in the part Mazandaran and Guilon near the Caspian Sea of the sea southern shores around wide spread Mazandarans the number about 4 million, berries the number while about 2-3 million people organize is enough This two of the people languages in Iran never how status have it's not and they are Persian language from their dialects is considered one . Both the nation is also Islam of religion Shiite sect belief they do

Lures and Bakhtiyori (Persian lor , bakhtiyārī) - semi-nomadic iranian nations . Basically of Iran western in the part wide spread Persia language in their dialects they talk . Lures the number approximately 4-8 million people , they are happy the number while approximately 150-200 thousand person organize is enough Basically of Islam shia sect belief do [9].

Pamir peoples - Eastern iranian languages and in dialects speaker nations . Basically of Tajikistan Pamir mountainous in the country , that's it including Mountain Badakhshan autonomous in the region , northeast In Afghanistan , in the north in Pakistan and of China Xinjiang-Uighur autonomous district in the southwest wide spread Pamir peoples the number each different to calculations 250-300 thousand according to person organize is enough Pamir peoples basically islam in religion Shiite sect Ismaili to the flow belief they do

Hazaras (hazōra) — Genghis Khan from the era the rest Mongolian of soldiers local population with mixed up to the body those who came descendants Basically Afghanistan mountainous in the regions wide spread Basically river language and Persian-Tajik languages in their dialects they talk . Hazaras basically of Islam Shiite sect belongs to and about 7 million people organize enough .

Horseshoes (داری . کاره ی ماق) - come output turkish was iranian semi-nomadic people Chows one how many to the tribes divided . Most big tribes these

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are : Jamshids , Feruzkohis , Taimans and Timur . Basically Afghanistan north-west and of Iran in the northeast wide spread Of the four common the number about 900 thousand person organize is enough Persia and river of tilarin different in their dialects they speak and basically of Islam Sunni and Shiite sects belongs to are considered

Flavors (tat, parsi , dagli , lohihion) - Caucasian wide spread out iranian people Language and come output according to another iranian of the nations less they differ . Of the flavors common the number about 50 thousand person and basically Azerbaijan , Iran and Russia northern in the Caucasus wide spread Basically islam of religion Shiite and Sunni sects belief they do

Tolishar (tol . tolyshon) — in Kavkazorty wide spread out iranian people Tolish come at the exit from Iranians except different Caucasus ethnic groups also participated . Tolish in the language they talk . Tolish common the number is different to calculations 260-800 thousand according to person organize is enough and basically Azerbaijan the south and of Iran in the north-west Guilon and Ardabil provinces wide spread Basically of Islam Sunni and Shiite sects belongs to are considered

Ossetians (oset . ir , irættæ) - another iranian of the nations distinguishable come output iranian people Ossetian in the language they talk . Ossetians common the number about 700 thousand person organize is enough and basically Russia North Ossetia - Alania Republic of Georgia contained South Ossetia autonomous region , Syria and in Turkey wide spread Ossetians main part Christian of religion Orthodoxy to the flow belief they do

Summary by doing so to speak, Iranian nations many in the regions residence by doing is coming Current at the time Iranian nations basically Iran , Afghanistan and Tajikistan , partially Uzbekistan , Pakistan , Turkey , Azerbaijan , Iraq , Syria , South Russia , Georgia and China in the regions wide spread , their anthropological and linguistic in terms of to be studied interest increased is going.

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